

Impact of workplace bullying on employee intentions to leave and mediating role of employee engagement: an empirical study from educational sector of Wuhan

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ABSTRACT: Employee intentions to leave may entail expensive consequences for the organizational. This study examined the mediating impact of employee engagement between the relationship of workplace bullying and employee intentions to leave. This study adopts quantitative approach to find relationship between variables. The data was collected from educational sector of Wuhan through random sampling technique using self-administered questionnaire where 350 was the sample. Structural equation modeling analysis showed that employee engagement substantially mediates the relationship between workplace bullying and intention to leave organization. However, workplace bullying and intention to leave the organization is positively associated. The results were integrated from a conservation of resources perspective and recommendations for practice were made.

Keywords: Workplace bullying, employee intentions to leave, employee engagement, educational sector, Wuhan, China.

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1. Introduction

Employees' turnover is one of the critical issues of any affiliation. Employees' intentions to leave is undeniable and an exorbitant issue in the organization (Tan et al., 2019), and the comparable is furthermore substantial for the educational sector of China. Organizations spend a lot on their employees in terms of developing, maintaining, training and retaining them in the organization. Therefore, it is mandatory for the top management to do all to retain employees in their respective organizations (Ongori, 2007). Standing out from other assist affiliations, educational establishments with having seen a high and lopsided employee turnover rate. Experts have perceived issues, for instance, low compensation, impolite extensive stretches of work, dull designs for finishing work and less opportunities for calling improvement (Barron, 2008; Walsh & Taylor, 2007) for turnover in the educational business. Due to the high costs associated with finding and training new employees it will decrease the productivity and engagement of current employees. The

increased workload demands leading to incidents of burnout and exhaustion as well as perceptions of workplace bullying, turnover intentions may have costly consequences for businesses (James & Matthew, 2012; Kumar & Dhamodaran, 2013). It has been communicated that with following progression of staff working in the educational business, employees favor occupations that have an unrivaled workplace (Paul and Kee, 2020). For more than twenty years, workplace bullying has been comprehensively thought of (Einarsen et al., 2018; Sheehan et al., 2020; Bergbom et al., 2015); nevertheless, regardless of it has been communicated by experts as "misunderstood characteristic" (Branch et al., 2013). Workplace bullying unfavorably impacts 10% to 20% of employees reliably, and in several workplaces, the impact of workplace bullying is on most of the employees (Einarsen et al., 2018). Workplace bullying is defined as unwelcome negative behaviour (verbal or nonverbal), actions, and incidents that take place frequently (weekly, for example), over a long period of time (for instance, for about six months), and have the potential to cause psychological, emotional, or physical discomfort (Einarsen & Raknes, 1997). According to Einarsen, Hoel, Zapf, and Cooper (2003), bullying conduct comprises acts of harassment that are offensive, socially exclude someone, or have a negative impact on their ability to perform their job. The ominous effect isn't limited to individual employees however then again is on the definitive and social structure (Einarsen et al., 2018). Currently, bullying is a huge social issue with unfavorable outcomes ordinary in affiliations (Einarsen et al., 2018). With overall advancement of educational region and affirmation of the impact of employee turnover on affiliation's show (Hinkin and Tracey, 2000), research in this space have dissected the groundworks of employees' intentions to leave (Karatepe, 2012). With a rising turnover of talented workforce, affiliations are focusing in on upkeep frameworks to help in the serious market (Lockwood, 2006). In the educational region, holding perfect and useful staff is a reliable wellspring of stress for trained professionals. Since education is the key for progress of country the educational region, contain extra energetic employees, thusly growing turnover rates is more fundamental to check in the educational region out. In any case, there is several investigations focusing in on the models to predict the point of the employee to remain or leave (Abugre, 2022; Kim and Jogaratnam, 2010) and its connected factors. Generally, the variable like workplace associations has mulled over with the positive outcome as occupation execution (Razzaghian and Ghani, 2014). Workplace bullying is such an approach to acting that makes fear among employees. They feel their self-exposed and defenseless and ends up being apprehensive and stressed. Which naturally lead down the resolve of employees, subsequently the interest of utilize in the gig turns out to be less and work disappointment builds, the exhibition of employee's perhaps stoppage, the devotion factor for the association of the employees likewise diminishes consequently these all variables lead to the increment of utilize turnover expectations. Employee turnover is a conjoint issue in emerging nations, solely in higher foundations. Employee turnover aim proceed as an option in contrast to genuine employee turnover. One of the difficult issues looked by educational establishments in China today is the way to deal with the changing employee boss relationship, Turnover has been a focal point of misgiving for HR the board experts for some time and holding of their top ability has been and keeps on excess their need. The previous many years have been the nastiest period for the universities in China in holding their employees. Maintenance of university and school speakers in China is an extraordinary test. Thusly, holding of competent and qualified teachers is imperative in universities achievement and positioning. This has included pressure the policymakers to think of serious HRM mediations to hold their speakers and guarantee the conveyance of great exploration and instructing. The quantity of employees who need to leave their place of employment because of workplace bullying is expanding. The subtleties of workplace bullying and its impact on aim to leave and how utilize commitment go about as middle person between these two is given in the article (Rasool et al., 2021). There has been seen

a lot of turnovers of employees in China. Employees frequently don't show dedication with their association exceptionally in educational establishments through this examination, it's had the option to tell anyway workplace bullying relates with one's turnover goals in educational organizations and how utilize commitment intercedes their connection. In past investigates creators recommended the scientists that future examination could be exploratory toward the connections among these elements and workplace bullying and feasible hierarchical execution utilizing position disappointment or occupation burnout as an intervening variable (Rasool et al., 2021).

Objectives of the Study

This study consists of the subsequent specific objectives:

- To understand how workplace bullying impacts employee intention to leave educational sector.
- To study the impact of workplace bullying on employee engagement in educational sector.
- To analyse the impact of employee engagement on employee intention to leave educational sector.
- To find the mediating impact of employee engagement on the relationship between workplace bullying and employee intention to leave educational sector.

2. Literature Review

Workplace bullying

Workplace bullying might be a persevering pattern from others inside the workplace that causes either physical or profound harm it embraces such ways as verbal, nonverbal, mental, and actual maltreatment The main recognized recorded utilization of "workplace bullying" is in 1992 in a very book by Andrea Adams known as *Bullying at Work: a method for facing and Survive* However there are numerous meanings of workplace bullying by various writers, most definitions truly do share an occasional topic. Saunders et al. (2007) arranged these definitions into four fundamental circumstances: (1) the unfortunate result of the conduct on the beneficiary, (2) the event and (3) the continuation of the way of behaving, and (4) the power imbalance coming about because of the way of behaving. While there is no single generally acknowledged meaning of workplace bullying, the proper definition by the Workplace Bullying Establishment (2014) characterized workplace bullying as "rehashed, well-being hurting abuse of at least one people (the objectives) by at least one culprit. A harmful lead incorporates undermining, embarrassing, work obstruction, damage and boisterous attack which keep work from finishing" (Tag-Eldeen et al., 2017). Studies have been done to investigate the causes of bullying. Two basic study philosophies are used to understand the causes of workplace bullying throughout the literature. The work environment hypothesis is the first strategy (Leymann, 1996). The work environment hypothesis claims that bullying at work is caused by unfavourable psychosocial working conditions, including work-related stressors (Bowling & Beehr, 2006), unfavourable work features (Broeck, Baillien, & Witte, 2011), and an excessive workload and time crunch (Ekici & Beder, 2014). Workplace bullying is characterized as rehashed habits coordinated by at least one employee that causes shame, infringement, and enduring, and that might influence work achievement to such an extent that the negative activities could guide to an unfriendly workspace. Moreover, the bullying way of behaving should put casualties in a substandard point of view where protecting themselves goes out to be troublesome. Nonetheless, such lead incorporates bullying, public embarrassment, terrorizing, horrendous ridiculing, disparaging of one's viewpoint, social prohibition, and irritating actual contact. As indicated by Einarsen et al. (2010) "Bullying at work imply that irritating,

affronting, socially barring someone or adversely moving somebody's work undertakings. so concerning the name bullying to be applied to a chosen movement, cooperation, or technique, it's to happen more than once and frequently and over the measure of your time. Bullying is partner raised strategy inside the course of the individual face lands up in partner second rate position and turns into the objective of deliberate negative social go about as Akella (2016) contends in her review, workplace bullying is monotonous and constant negative activities which plan to threaten or hurt the objective or casualty. This establishes a climate of dread, trouble, and power irregularity. She further contended that the different social standards have a huge connection with social propensities. Social orders which were positioned higher in power distance and lower vulnerability aversion will generally be more defenseless to bullying (Carpio-Indama and Carpio, 2020).

Turnover intentions / intentions to leave

Turnover intentions/intentions to leave concerning laborers turnover intentions, the welcome area is one in every one of the world's quickest developing enterprises. with regards to Cho et al. (2009), turnover intentions suggest to one's intention to withdraw his utilizing association that shows a break inside the connection among laborers and thusly the association (Taq-Eldeen et al., 2017). The costs of turnover embrace cost, preparation, and reselection and lessen the resolve of current laborers which can prompt serious misfortunes in the organizations (Cho et al., 2009; Taq-Eldeen et al., 2017). Employee turnover is the leaving of a member of an organization who was getting compensation from the organization (Mobley, 1982). There are several reasons why employees leave their jobs, including personal issues (unhappiness at work owing to other personal performance), organizational factors (workplace culture, benefits package, and leadership style), and external considerations (un-employment and staffing). (Vandenberg & Nelson, 1999). Numerous study projects were carried out to comprehend the problems with staff turnover. In depth explanation of the psychological process of quitting and withdrawing from an organization was stated by Mobley in 1982. Regarding his withdrawal process, a person first evaluates his current position to see if he is satisfied with it or not; if he is not, quitting is next considered. Lacity et al. (2008) previously mentioned that turnover might be an arranged way of behaving of employees to withdraw from the association. with regards to Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) intention to turnover is addressed as an employee's conduct intention to leave the association. Inside the gift concentrate, we tend to utilize the meaning of Tett and Meyer (1993), who illustrated turnover as a mindful and strong container of laborers to withdraw their association. This study thought about the opportunity of employees' intention to withdraw from the foundation as a crucial design result of bullying. Foundations payloads based on their laborers in conditions of their enlistment and training (Ongori, 2007). In this way, specialist turnover is truly significant for any association. There's a strong relationship between workplace bullying and casualties' renunciation from the association Employee turnover is an endemic issue in the advanced education area in Africa. Employee turnover intention goes about as a substitute for genuine employee turnover. One of the difficult issues looked by universities today is the way to deal with the changing business relationship. As indicated by Tandung (2016), turnover intention makes sense of the overall strength of a singular's motivation or aim toward willful super durable withdrawal from an association. Essentially a rationale or reason drives an employee to stop from their ongoing workplace. Saeed et al. (2014) makes sense of the turnover of an employee as the revolution of laborers between the state of work and joblessness, occupations and occupations around the work market and firms.

Employee engagement

Employee engagement is a source of a carnal and thoughtful association between employees and the association It regulates employees' own ideas to the vision of the

connotation, which expands the efficiency of the employees and, thus, the association. A draw in employee is even and genuinely associated with the vision and mission of the association, which depicts and administers the contribution of the employee to the hierarchical objectives (Rasool et al., 2021). A draw in an employee will work with a dynamic demeanor, which will construct the standing and worth of the association. Associations develop conditions to empower and enjoy the extraordinary engagement of employees and draw in employees who are energetic and pretty much all help from their associations. Associations characterize exceptional plans to draw in employees, which adjusts laborer objectives to those of the associations. Employee engagement is a positive technique to stay balanced and detachment of the employees and enjoy their feelings into inspiration and disparaged moral way of behaving in the work environment. Employee engagement gain much recognition of professionals as the engaged employee 's attitude and behavior are different from unengaged employees. From last two decades employee engagement is a new concept with respect to academicians in the domain of management studies. (Rafferty, Maben, West & Robinson, 2005; Ellis & Sorensen, 2007). Employee engagement is associated with other organizational behavior but it gained a lot more recognition among these behaviors. Previous researches of (Burmam & Zeplin, 2005; Saks, 2006; Slatten & Mehmetoglu, 2011) differentiated employee engagement from commitment, involvement, organizational citizenship behavior and job satisfaction. Engagement incorporates commitment and satisfaction. Employee engagement is a two-way process although, commitment and satisfaction are one way process (Rafferty et al, 2005). Employee Engagement is a greater source of attachment for individuals as compared to organizational commitment. Organizational commitment portrays employees' attitude and attachment with their respective organization whereas employee engagement exhibit not only attitude but it also includes employee's absorption and attentiveness in their performances (Juhdi, Pawan & Hansaram, 2013; Saks, 2006). Employee engagement is also a different concept with regard to organizational citizenship behavior as organization citizenship behavior is a voluntary behavior to help the organization and engagement is an obligatory and formal behavior (Saks, 2006). Saks (2006) argued that employee engagement comprised of cognitive, behavioral and emotional elements which is associated with employee 's performance at work. Holbeche and Springett (2003) assert that there is a direct correlation between employees' assessments of the "meaning" of their jobs and their levels of engagement and ultimately performance. They contend that people actively look for meaning in their work, and if employers don't try to provide it, they will leave. According to the study's findings, more people seek meaning in their jobs than in other areas of their lives. According to Holbeche and Springett (2003), high levels of participation are only possible at workplace where there is a sense of commitment which binds people with emotions and aspirations.

Hypothesis development

Workplace bullying and Employee Engagement

There are numerous confirmations from past assessments that shows a basic association flanked by workplace bullying and employee engagement as demonstrated by Bakker and Albrecht (2018), a draw an employee is a convinced, free, and contributive part who tends to a significant extension to the HR and advances various leveled advancement and improvement. Ramesh (2021) organizes employee engagement into two sorts: work engagement and legitimate engagement. Work engagement prompts employee obligation, which clearly oversees responsibility and works execution, which courses a progressive development. Progressive engagement is interlaced with employee obligation and employee devotion. The previous composing maintains the view that the impact of workplace bullying on the relationship of the individual, work satisfaction, and vivacious characteristics for work is negative, while employee engagement and progressive

engagement are repulsively influenced (Arnetz et al., 2018). What's more, COR speculation similarly maintains the negative association between workplace bullying and employee engagement. Along these lines, hence, the form of employee engagement is generally associated with a hurtful workplace environment and can be estimated as follows:

H1: Workplace bullying is negatively related to employee engagement.

Workplace bullying and intention to leave

Bullying refers as a negative intense approach to acting which is excess and exact (Einarsen et al., 2018). This every now and again unfavorably impacts a singular's work task. The possibility of workplace bullying was familiarized in a speculative assessment (Leymann, 1990). This prompt goading and moreover socially excepting an individual, consequently, it has should be a "more crushing and obliterating issue for employees than any leftover kinds of business-related pressure set up" (Einarsen et al., 2018). Lately, academics and policymakers have been enthused about workplace bullying seeing its high unfriendly result on employees (a setback from bullying) which has not been satisfactorily examined. According to the COR speculation, the goal of workplace bullying will be energized to apportion his/her resources (Rodríguez-Muñoz et al., 2015), which could achieve the reason for employees to leave the affiliation. Experts in their assessments have communicated the association between different psychosocial factors and bullying (Johan Hauge et al., 2007; Mathisen et al., 2008). Bullying at work is a problem that plagues modern employment. Workplace bullying is defined as "harassing, offending, socially excluding someone or negatively influencing someone's work" (Einarsen, Hoel, Zapf, and L, 2003). To qualify as bullying, behaviour must be persistent, ongoing, and the result of one or more people, and the victim must find it impossible to defend themselves or escape the hostile environment (Einarsen & Skogstad, 1996).

According to Tett and Meyer (1993), an employee's intention to quit a company is characterized as a conscious and deliberate decision, and it may be a reliable indicator of actual turnover behaviors. There are several reasons why employees leave their jobs. Stress at work is one of the main causes (Elçi, Ener, Kürü, & Alpkan, 2012). Workplace bullying has been found to unfavorably impact lead perspectives, similar to work satisfaction, workplace bullying, and bunch execution, achieving a higher intention among employees (loss) to leave work (Mathisen et al., 2008; Devonish, 2013; Nielsen & Einarsen, 2012). Therefore, it has been hypothesized that:

H2: Workplace Bullying has a significant relationship with Intention to leave.

Mediating Effect of Employee engagement

As indicated by the expectation of various explicit investigations, workplace bullying adversely impacts employee engagement (Rasool et al., 2021). Past examinations have revealed that the existence of a harmful workplace climate compromises the prosperity of employees. For example, various examinations have proposed a positive relationship between workplace bullying and unfortunate prosperity (Einarsen et al., 2018). Engagement at work has been demonstrated to have a range of beneficial consequences, including on job performance, effectiveness and creativity (Halbesleben, 2010). Therefore, managers at all levels of the business should be concerned about issues that lower employee engagement in their work. As bullying is difficult to deal with and causes a sustained mental strain on the victim, it counts as a hindrance. Bullying hurts employee engagement at work because it tells them they're not respected and valued. Therefore, a negative correlation between being exposed to bullying and work engagement may be anticipated. Employee turnover intention is significantly and favorably impacted by employee work engagement. Many researches have concurred that work engagement is a significant factor determining employees' intention to leave their jobs, especially given the amount of attention being paid to this sector (Langford, 2009). Additionally, empirical research has

provided enough evidence to support the relationship between work engagement and organizational outcomes including job satisfaction, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship performance, and intention to leave an organization (Munish & Agarwal, 2017; Javed, Gulzar, Hussain, 2015; Langford, 2009). According to Ram and Prabhakar (2011), employee involvement is related to their perspectives, objectives, and activities. Employee engagement significantly affects organizational outcomes, worker productivity, ease of hiring, and employee retention. Rajalingam (2020) indicated that workplace bullying outcome in more prominent pressure and lower fulfillment degrees among personnel who have been exposed to it. Bullying at work has a detrimental impact on employees' feelings of worth and belonging in their work groups and may result in job feature loss. Threats of social exclusion and feelings of self-worthiness can also be conveyed to victims of bullying (Zapf, 1999). These messages convey to the victim that he or she is not viewed as a noble person and is valued less within the organization (Shrauger & Jones, 1968; Schimel, Arndt, Pyszczynski, & Greenberg, 2001; Penhaligon, Louis & Restubog, 2013). Members of the group may feel less a sense of identity as a result of social exclusion and rejection, which will make the victims question their value to the company and raise their risk of losing their jobs. It has also been suggested that employee retention is closely related to work engagement. Christian, Garza, and Slaughter (2014) state that "engaged workers experience a high degree of connectedness with their work duties, they strive for job-related goals that are interwoven with their task definitions and scripts, leading to high levels of task performance." According to Karatepe (2013), work engagement has a favourable impact on both the work performance and extra-role behaviour of hotel employees. In addition, Salanova, Agut, and Peiro (2005) found a relationship between performance and engagement among workers in restaurants and hotels that was mediated by the service atmosphere. These results are also supported by a more recent meta-study. Work engagement was linked to performance, which can be explained by positive employees who have the motivation to complete duties successfully. Subsequently, being harassed while working is a danger to mental prosperity too, and employees who are exposed to bullying report more noteworthy degrees of conventional and psychological pressure and can't be participated in work appropriately (Taq-Eldeen et al., 2017). Likewise, workplace bullying has additionally been adversely connected to employee engagement since it prompts upgraded degrees of occupation pressure and close-to-home fatigue.

H3: Employee engagement has mediating relationship between workplace bullying and turnover intentions of employ

Figure 1. Research model

3. Research Methodology

The targeted population was the teachers and admin staff of educational institute from Wuhan city China. The exact total number of populations was unknown that's why non-probability sampling technique was used. Due to restriction of physically approach to respondents and to maintain social distance, population was approached through email and personal contacts through online survey form (google form). That's why the questionnaire was made online to float and email easier to collect data. 350 sample size was targeted to accumulate data because to run the SEM even 100 sample size is enough as suggested by many statisticians (Mundfrom et al., 2005). Stratified sampling technique was applied to obtain a representative sample. The survey has been conducted between June to September 2022.

Data Analysis and Results

To test the hypotheses, the author used the survey consists of three sections. The foremost section assessed the items of workplace bullying; the next section assessed the items of intention to leave, and the third section assessed by employee engagement. All the items are assessed with the same five-point Likert Scale ranging from 5 = strongly agree to 1 = strongly disagree. The value of Cronbach's α for WB was 0.940 which was significant. The items measured were 21 adapt from (Razzaghian & Ghani, 2014). The value of Cronbach's α for ITL was 0.830 which was also significant. And consist of 3 items again adopted from (Razzaghian & Ghani, 2014), 5 items for employee engagement were adapted from (Jha & Kumar, 2016). The value of Cronbach's α for EE was 0.94, which was also a significant value.

Table 1. Demographic profile

Profile	Category	%age
Gender	Male	62
	Female	38
Education	Graduate	48
	Masters	52

For data analysis, a two-step approach is used (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988). To evaluate the consistency of the measurements, Composite Reliability (CR) and Cronbach's alphas were calculated. In order to determine the discriminating and convergent validity, Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and factor loading were tested. A relevant SEM to evaluate the relationship between the constructs was analyzed after verification of the measurement model. For statistical analysis, SPSS 26.0 and Smart PLS 3.0 were applied. First, CFA projected a measurement model. All latent constructs were loaded for correlation analysis with their appropriate measurement items and constructs (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988). Composite reliability and the Cronbach's alpha have been determined. The analysis uses three constructs. Alpha estimates fall in the range from 0.94 to 0.95 for all elements. The alpha values of all the constructs that meet the minimum requirement of 0.70 are shown in table 3. Composite reliability values surpass the 0.70 standard value, varying from 0.95 to 0.96. The instrument is now reliable in this analysis for the calculation of the latent construct. Standardized Factor Loading varied from 0.71 to 0.90 for all items, which is important at the significance level of 0.01. Overall, convergent validity satisfied all the values. All AVE values fall within the range of 0.65 to 0.67, which was above the lowest criterion of 0.50, which revealed that structures perceive the highest variance (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Items	SFL	A
Workplace Bullying		0.940
WB1	0.604	
WB2	0.7	
WB3	0.7	
WB4	0.603	
WB5	0.621	
WB6	0.7	
WB7	0.75	
WB8	0.73	
WB9	0.7	
WB10	0.7	
WB11	0.7	
WB12	0.7	
WB13	0.7	
WB14	0.7	
WB15	0.71	
WB16	0.728	
WB17	0.726	
WB18	0.718	
WB19	0.7	
WB20	0.63	
Intention to leave		0.830
ITL1	0.79	
ITL2	0.915	
ITL 3	0.924	
ITL 4	0.852	
Employee engagement		0.904
EE1	0.844	
EE 2	0.824	
EE 3	0.894	
EE 4	0.844	

AVE values were correlated with square correlations among paired constructs to assess discriminant validity and reflect discriminant validity (see Table 3). In summary, high validity and consistency for the role of the latent build are demonstrated by the test instrument.

Table 3: Correlation matrix

	1	2	3
WB	0.80		
ITL	0.551	0.72	0.94
EE	0.618	0.83	
Mean	3.8671	3.84	3.65
SD	0.77	0.8	0.92

Table 4: Model estimation

Hypothesized path	Path coefficient	T value
ITL->EE	0.554	8.54
WB->EE	0.321	5.43
WB->ITL	0.555	8.98

In order to assess the fitness of the model for CFA, the Chi-square test and several fit indices were run. The CFI was which is close to the standard value recommended by the Chi-square fit quality of 3360 (Bentler, 1990). The NFI (NormedFit Index) was 0.7. The results indicated that the models' overall fitness was a satisfactory fit that is statistically less than a perfect 1.0 (Bentler, 1990). The parameter estimates revealed that WB and EE $b=0.321$, $t=5.43$, positively and significantly as shown in table 5, the WB and ITL parameter revealed that $b=0.55$ and $t=8.98$ positively and significantly supported each other so thus hypothesis 1 is supported. The 3rd parameter EE and ITL estimates and revealed that $b=0.554$ and $t=8.54$. Mediating role of EE between WB and ITL: The investigators used the Sobel test to verify the mediator's importance and found that there was a substantial mediation impact between the WB and ITL on EE (table 5) ($z=75.37$ and $p= 0.00001$). Thus hypothesis 2 shows the mediation effect of EE between WB and ITL is accepted.

Table 5: Sobel test

Hypothesis path	Predictor	mediator	outcome	z value	p value	Status
WB→EE→ITL	WB	EE	ITL	75.37	0.00001	accepted

WB=workplace bullying, ITL= intentions to leave, EE= employ engagement

Figure 2. Purposed pls model

4. Discussion & Conclusion

A toxic workplace environment and employee engagement have attracted the attention of many researchers. Previously, such kind of studies were conducted in advanced nations. This is the first study to be conducted in an emerging nation like China. Moreover, it is also the first study to be conducted amongst employees of educational sector of Wuhan city of China. First, the direct impact of workplace bullying on employees intention to leave was determined. This hypothesis was inversely approved that it directly influence employees intentions to leave organization (Ramesh, 2021). Secondly, we investigated negative effect of workplace bullying on EE. This hypothesis was also support with statistical results. Many studies support this claim that WB negatively impact on EE. Thirdly, we inquired that how EE influence ITL of employees. Jha and Kumar (2016) indicated that EE has positive influence on ITL which help them to retain in organization. Similarly, previous studies also support the results of current study (Saeed et al., 2014; Ramesh, 2021; Akella, 2016; Paul et al., 2020). So the above discussion proves that EE reduces the toxic effect of WB on employees to leave the organization.

Managerial Implications

The research provided gives realistic contributions in many ways to teachers and management. Firstly, managers would grab initiatives to donot support and WB activities in the organization. For the achievement of the organizational objective, the top management must manage its assets and competencies in the utmost proficient way

Limitations

While our results are robust and significant, there are several limitations that need to be recognized explicitly. The foremost drawback (limitation) of this research is that data collect from a developing country and one city of a province. The shortcomings of this analysis can also be related to the suggested model and its consequences. In addition, the control variables in this context are also used.

Future Research

Although, this research limitation shows that this study can expand by appending more practices like Teamwork, environmental performance, green orientation, etc. Future researchers add Control variables like firm age, size, ISO standards,etc. The same research was also conducted in other developed countries to find generalize results. In the future, the researchers can append this framework by using an organizational commitment, employee commitment as a mediator.

Author Contributions:

“Conceptualization, X.X. and Y.Y.; methodology, X.X.; software, X.X.; validation, X.X., Y.Y. and Z.Z.; formal analysis, X.X.; investigation, X.X.; resources, X.X.; data curation, X.X.; writing—original draft preparation, X.X.; writing—review and editing, X.X.; visualization, X.X.; supervision, X.X.; project administration, X.X.; funding acquisition, Y.Y. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript

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